

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15151368>

THE IMPACT OF PHILOSOPHICAL THINKING ON NEW APPROACHES IN MEDICINE

Umirzakova Nargiza Akmalovna,

Associate Professor, (PhD), Department of Social Sciences with a course in bioethics
Tashkent State Dental Institute,
n.a.umirzakova@mail.ru

***Abstract:** In the modern era, profound transformations are taking place in science and technology, including in the field of medicine and biology. They require a broad philosophical analysis, since their application concerns not only issues of health and illness, but also the phenomena of life and death, which are originally philosophical problems. In this article, the author focuses on the relationship between medicine and philosophy. In particular, the article examines the ethical and philosophical aspects of medicine through the prism of understanding medical practice through human values and ethical principles.*

***Keywords:** philosophical thinking, ethical conflicts, human values, life, death, health, illness, medical practice, medical approaches.*

ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ ФИЛОСОФСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ НА НОВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В МЕДИЦИНЕ

***Аннотация:** В эпоху современности в науке и в технике, в том числе в сфере медицины и биологии происходят глубокие преобразования. Они требуют широкого философского анализа, так как их применение касается не только вопросов здоровья и болезни, но и феноменов жизни и смерти,*

являющихся исконно философскими проблемами. В данной статье автор акцентирует своё внимание на взаимоотношения между медициной и философией. В частности, в статье изучены этические и философские аспекты медицины сквозь призму понимания медицинской практики через человеческие ценности и этические принципы.

Ключевые слова: философское мышление, этические конфликты, человеческие ценности, жизнь, смерть, здоровье, болезнь, медицинская практика, медицинские подходы.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of philosophical thinking on views in the field of medicine and to study the place of human values, moral criteria and philosophy of life in medicine. In the process of treatment, the main values for doctors, patients' rights, ethical issues, themes of life and death are considered through a philosophical approach [2]. At the same time, the study also aims to determine the ethical basis of the relationship between a doctor and a patient. As modern medical technologies develop, the philosophical approach to ethical issues becomes even more important. Thus, the main goal of the study is to scientifically substantiate the importance of the philosophical approach in the field of medicine.

The study used scientific sources studying the influence of philosophical thinking on medical approaches, modern philosophical and medical literature, as well as studies including basic theories in the field of ethics and bioethics [3]. Among these sources, a special place is occupied by the works of M. Foucault, Aristotle and modern bioethicists. The methodological approach used was theoretical analysis, empirical observation and inductive approach. The study collected examples of interactions between doctors and patients, ethical conflicts and ethical problems arising from the use of modern medical technologies. The ethical foundations of modern medicine have been widely analyzed using philosophical analysis and comparative research methods as research methods[2]. The analysis showed that philosophical thinking is important for doctors when making decisions in the

treatment process. For example, philosophical approaches can be used to find ethical solutions to complex issues such as life and death decisions [1], the use of donors in transplantation, and obtaining patient consent. Philosophical thinking also helps to prioritize universal values in the field of medicine, which leads to the formation of trusting relationships between patients and doctors [5]. The results of the study show that philosophical approaches in medical research serve to make the treatment process more humane, humane and play an important role in improving the psychological state of patients. Philosophical thinking shapes not only practical but also ethical approaches in medicine. Today, in modern medicine, views on human life and death, family and society, and individual rights play an important role in making medical decisions. From this point of view, ethical approaches based on philosophical thinking are necessary in such areas as patient consent, donor issues, the use of artificial intelligence, and the use of new technologies. In modern medicine, it is important to consider the impact of medical technologies on the patient's condition in the process of making ethical decisions. Philosophy and ethics are an integral part of medicine, and it is necessary to develop new approaches to increase the positive impact of modern technologies on human health.

Thus, this study focused on identifying the place of philosophical thinking in medicine and how it influences human values, ethical issues and the doctor-patient relationship. A philosophical approach helps to put human values first in medicine, allows taking into account the mental state of patients and opens up opportunities for making medical decisions from a humanitarian point of view. Moreover, the importance of philosophy in developing ethical and moral criteria for doctors is incomparable.

In order to preserve universal human values and develop ethical approaches in society, it is important to maintain a holistic connection between philosophical thinking and medicine in modern medicine [4].

List of references:

1. Н.А.Умирзакова, У.М.Исмаилов. Влияние цифровых технологий на диагностику и лечение: Телемедицина, приложения для мониторинга здоровья // Academic research in educational sciences, 2025. - С.229-233.
2. Adams, R. Philosophical Foundations of Medicine. - Cambridge University Press, - 2022.
3. N.A.Umirzakova, A.K.Jaloliddinov. Methodological aspect of the relationship of philosophy and medicine: A new level of communication of philosophy and medicine // World scientific research journal. Том 9/ №2. P. 58-60.
4. Н.А.Умирзакова, С.Д. Инагамова. Решение этических проблем медицины в условиях цифровизации // GOLDEN BRAIN, 2025/3/15/ Том 3. №4. С. 94-100.
5. Н.А. Умирзакова. В.Р.Поттернинг глобал биоэтика концепцияси. // Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, Том 2, №11, 2022. - Б.371-380.